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First Dissociation Constant of Succinic Acid from 0° to 50° by e.m.f. Method Based on Modified Davies Equation

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PINCHING and Bates¹ measured the e.m.f. of the cells of the type,

and calculated first dissociation constant, K_1 of succinic acid from 0° to 50° at 5 degrees interval. Since, K_1/K_2 for succinic acid is about 25, they used many approximations in the calculation for overlapping equilibria. Moreover, the method of computation of first dissociation constant was much complicated.

In the present communication, values for K_1 from 0° to 50° at 5 degrees interval were recalculated on the basis of modified Davies equation proposed by Prasad².

Results and Discussion

The electromotive force of the cell (C-1) can be given by

$$m_{\text{H}^+} = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{(E^\circ - E)F}{2.30259RT} + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \log m_{\text{Cl}^-} - \beta\mu \right] \dots (1)$$

Here, β for the cell (C-1) containing solution of HCl and NaHSuc will have the same value as in pure HCl, provided the ionic strength, μ does not exceed beyond 0.2³⁻⁴. The reaction between H^+ and HSuc^- ions in cell (C-1) cannot go to

completion because of dissociation of molecular succinic acid (H_2Suc).

Further, the hydrogen ion concentration, m_{H^+} is not large enough in cell (C-1) to prevent the second step dissociation,

From application of electrical neutrality in solutions of the cell (C-1),

$$m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} + m_{\text{Cl}^-} = m_{\text{H}^+} + m_{\text{Na}^+}$$

It follows,

$$m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} = m_{\text{H}^+} + 0.5 \text{ m} \dots (4)$$

Equation (3) can be represented by

$$\frac{m_{\text{Suc}^-}}{m_{\text{HSuc}^-}} = \text{antilog} \left[(\log K_2 - \beta_2\mu) + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \log m_{\text{H}^+} \right] \dots (5)$$

For computation of molalities of separate entity present in cell (C-1), an arbitrary value was assigned to μ in equation (1) and the corresponding value for m_{H^+} was found out. In the above recalculation, E° due to Harned & Ehlers⁵, β due to Sinha, Ghosh & Prasad⁶ and E due to Pinching & Bates¹ were taken. The value of m_{H^+} thus obtained was fed into equations (4) and (5) and the corresponding values for m_{HSuc^-} and m_{Suc^-} were calculated. Values for $\log K_2$ and β_2 for equation (5) were taken from author's earlier work⁶.

Since the ionic strength, μ of solution in cell (C-1) is given by,

$$\mu = 1.75 \text{ m} + 1.5 m_{\text{H}^+} - 0.5 m_{\text{HSuc}^-} \dots (6)$$

a fresh value for μ was calculated by substituting the above values. This fresh value of μ was again fed in equation (1) and the corresponding value of m_{H^+} was calculated. The above process of successive approximation was repeated till constancy in values for m_{H^+} , m_{HSuc^-} , m_{Suc^-} and μ were obtained up to 6th place of decimal. The value of $m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}}$ was calculated from equation (7) obtained from the consideration of total succinate entities present in cell (C-1),

$$1.5 \text{ m} = m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + m_{\text{Suc}^-} + m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}} \dots (7)$$

The equilibrium (2) can be represented by

$$\log \frac{m_{\text{H}^+} - m_{\text{HSuc}^-}}{m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}}} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - \beta_1\mu \dots (8)$$

where K_1 is the first dissociation constant and $\beta_1 = (\beta_{\text{H}^+} + \beta_{\text{HSuc}^-})$. The L.H.S. of equation (8) were plotted against μ , when straight lines were obtained

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